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**PULSE RATE-ENABLED WEARABLE HUMAN TRACKING SYSTEM WITH
BOUNCE GEOLOCATOR**

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ABSTRACT

Over the years Nigeria and many African countries have been challenged by the menace of kidnapping, banditry, and insurgency. Many times, a ransom was obtained from the relations of the victims only to find out their loved ones were killed despite the urge amount paid as ransom. This research, therefore, proposes a pulse rate-enabled human tracking system that sends distress messages to relatives and security agents about the current location and pulse rate of the victim in case of an emergency. The device uses portable sensors interface with a microcontroller to acquire sensor readings which are wirelessly transmitted to relevant stakeholders within seconds. The uniqueness of the developed device is that apart from using the GPS information to locate the victim as achieved in previous studies, the pulse rate information received could be used by health personnel to know if the victim is still alive or not as well as the health status of such a victim whether weak, tired, anxious or dying. The device is also embedded with a bounce geolocator that allows the rescue or security agents to continually detect current collation of the victim by sending and receiving geolocation signals from orbital satellite. The proposed device will go a long way in planning a holistic rescue mission that can save a victim's life. The portability and ease of use of the developed device would make it a valuable tool in mitigating the challenge of insurgency, kidnapping, and banditry being experienced in Nigeria and many African countries.

Keywords: Pulse rate, wearable human tracking system, bounce geolocator, kidnapping, Geographical Positioning System

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1. Introduction

Kidnapping has become one of the most infamous crimes in the world, as it is now seen as a national security threat in a country like Nigeria. Kidnapping in Nigeria has become a serious problem for all people of different classes, ranging from educated to illiterate, wealthy and poor, rural and urban dwellers, government officials, and local farmers. Of recent, the kidnapping of hundreds of train passengers has been a dimension of kidnapping in the country with demands of high ransom payments (Nwite, 2023; Ojiego, 2022). It is evident from the news and eyewitnesses, that kidnapping has increased and has become a 'business' through which millions of naira are collected from victims and next of kin over time because of the seemingly helplessness of the security agents and government to tackle the problem with all seriousness it deserved (Ibrahim and Ahmad, 2020). Between July 2021 and June 2022, a total of N653.7 million was paid as ransom to kidnappers in Nigeria. According to (Odeniyi, 2022), 605 cases of abductions took place in January alone, with 1,202 deaths recorded while thousands of others sustained serious injuries. This indicates that the kidnapping has spread beyond the Niger Delta Region where it originates from to the rest of the country (Albert, Danjibo and Albert, 2020). In many of these cases, where a huge amount of money is paid as ransom to secure the release of victims; the relations of such victims sometimes are not able to ascertain if their loved ones are alive, their current locations, or their health status. Therefore, this research aims at mitigating these challenges. As this goes on, several notable Nigerians have appealed to government agencies to consider the use of modern technologies to quell the flame of insecurity in the nation (Dunno, 2021).

Different technologies are being used nowadays to solve the problem of the security of lives and properties. For instance, in (Khan et al., 2021), the authors used radio frequency identification (RFID) in form of a wearable wristband combined with Geographical positioning system (GPS) technology for tracking Hajj participants who come from different countries in Saudi Arabia for pilgrimage. In other words, RFID had been used for tracking of human (Khan et al., 2021) vehicles (Ismail, et al., 2021; Maramis and Rompas, 2018; Dhanasekar et al., 2019), home security (Dusit and Norjali, 2021). Geographical positioning system (GPS) had been used extensively in the tracking of different devices including vehicles (Karthikeyan, 2021; Rahman et al., 2016; Abd Wahab et al., 2018), humans (Khan et al., (2021).

The tracking system in vehicles such as RFID (Ismail, et al., 2021; Ogidan et al., 2022) or GPS (Karthikeyan, 2021; Rahman et al., 2016; Abd Wahab et al., 2018; Ogidan et al., 2022) have not been very helpful in the fight against insecurity in the sense that, once people are abducted, the first thing is to whisk them from their vehicles into the bush. Valuables such as mobile devices are retrieved from them so that they will not be able to make calls to their loved ones or the security agencies. This now call for the use of other forms of tracking system that are portable and could be worn under clothes such that it would not be visible enough for the abductors to notice.

Wearable sensors with low costs could be a major solution to this problem with the hope of enhancing the tracking of the victim in real time. A sensor is a device that detects changes in its environment and transmits the information to other devices for processing (Sheldon, 2022). A sensor converts a physical parameter, such as temperature, pressure, or speed, into an

electrically measurable signal. A sensor is always used in conjunction with other devices. Wearable sensors are sensors embedded in wearable objects or clothing that come into contact with the body. Wearable sensors are defined in a variety of ways. These devices can be identified by their distinct features. Wearable computing is defined as data gathering and disseminating equipment that increases user productivity and is worn by the user while performing routine tasks (Randell, 2014).

It appears as clothes and accessories that incorporate computing capabilities to give users distinctive qualities. Systems made using wearable sensors and other components can transmit a warning message together with the victim's location and a pulse- or heartbeat-based confirmation of life. If a certain location needs to be known for safety tracking, this device can also be remotely activated to obtain that information. Because they would know where to look and could also tell other security formations nearby to execute a stop-and-search operation, this would offer the security agents an advantage. This can save the victims' families money by preventing a substantial ransom payment that might otherwise push them into bankruptcy, in addition to sparing the victims' lives.

Recently, the idea of remote monitoring has received a lot of attention, particularly in the telemedicine industry. The reliability of these devices is now better supported by more data, and the technology is more readily accessible. These gadgets have a range of sensors that can be used to track variables and send data to a portable device or an online data storage service. The variety of the sensors can be related to both their placements and the stimuli they respond to, such as bodily motions, organic substances, and physiological vital signs (Wu, 2021). These gadgets can influence decisions and convey information in real-time while connected to a smartphone, computer, or other wireless devices (Vijayan, 2021).

Several works are done with the use of wearable and smart body sensors, and are available in the literature. The ones with close relation to this work would be discussed in this literature review section.

Emem et al., 2022, worked on an IoT-Based wearable human protection system. The system which was an attempt to track the location of a kidnapped victim use Atmega 328P, a resistive sensor, and a push-button as main component. A user is expected to put on the device and is expected to press a push button to activate the system when the presence of danger is sensed. Once the system is activated, it sends an SMS that contain the current location of the user to a designated number, with an update every 10 minutes. The information in the message can be used to view the current location of the victim on Google Maps. The evaluation of the system revealed an average response time of 6.0 and 7.0 seconds for the Airtel and Globacom networks respectively.

The work of Akram, Jain and Hemalatha., 2019 entails the development of a smart safety device for women using IoT. The system is made up of LCD, GSM Module, Buzzer, Amega 328, and Fingerprint scanner. A user activates the system by placing finger on the fingerprint scanner when danger is sensed. Once the fingerprint of the user has been scanned, the system sends an SMS comprising the longitude and latitude of the user's location to designated security personnel and next of kin for emergency response. The system also raises an alarm for the people around that scene to understand that, the user is in distress and needs help. The user can use the shockwave generator of the system to temporarily knock down her attacker. A mobile

app of the system can also help a user to send messages including an audio record of her environment, and use the app to get to the nearest safe location. The prototype of the system was successfully developed, tested, and adjudged to work effectively according to the design. Booranawong, et al., 2018 developed a device-free human tracking detection and tracking system using a received signal strength indicator (RSSI) and tracking indicator for an indoor environment. The system has two main functions: a wireless communication system and a human detection and tracking system. While the second function is designed to detect and track the person using a predetermined threshold and a zone selection mechanism, the first function is built for measuring and collecting RSSI signals impacted by human presence and movement. The experimental findings demonstrate that the proposed technique can accurately identify and monitor human movements, and the proposed communication protocol may greatly improve communication reliability. Communication reliability is indicated by the packet delivery ratio, which is about 100%. In all instances of one-man motions, detection and tracking accuracy assessed by the number of times the approach can detect and track the human with the correct zone is almost 100%.

To ascertain if someone is still alive, doctors and other health workers have laid down procedures. One such is by testing if the person's heart is still working by checking the pulse (Everplans, 2022). As a way of assisting clinicians, (Khan et al., 2022) developed a device using IoT technology to measure the pulse of patients. The authors combined a pulse rate sensor and body temperature sensor to provide vital signals to the Arduino microcontroller. The pulse rate is read on the digital display of a Liquid Crystal Display (LCD).

The limitation of many of the methods reviewed in this work (Emem et al., 2022; 2022, Khan et al, 2019, Khan et al, 2021) is that even though many of them can send distress messages and notifications, to the victim loves ones or security agents, they cannot reveal if the victim is still alive or not neither are they able to reveal the health status of the person under consideration. The uniqueness of this work lies in the fact that it combines the geolocation of the user (victim) with the pulse rate information to provide the current location and possible health status of the victim – whether he is alive, weak, sick, tired, or dying. This presents vital information for the proper planning of a holistic rescue mission for the victim. The remaining part of the work is arranged as follows. The methodology is considered in Section 2, results in Section 3, discussion of results in Section 4 while Section 5 concludes the paper.

2. Methodology

The techniques used in the development of the pulse rate sensor-based human tracking system are described in this section. It includes an analysis of the design, materials, prototype development, and operation. It goes into great detail about how the system can be developed and used. This section shows the schematics and various diagrammatic representations of the sensor-based human tracking system and, in the end, discusses a case study scenario of its operation. The design is divided into two broad parts, that is the hardware and the software.

2.1 Hardware Requirements.

Figure 1 a is the block diagram; Figure 2 shows the components connected together. Figure 3 is the circuit diagram while Figure 4 is the flowchart of the developed system. The block diagram includes submodules such as the pulse rate sensor, capacitive touch sensor, and

A9G module that are linked to a microcontroller unit (Arduino Nano) powered by a lithium battery management system. These separate devices work and communicate together to form a system. The Pulse Sensor is usually attached to the fingertip or the earlobe to measure the heart rate. It has three pins namely Vcc, Ground, and Signal. It possesses an optical amplifying circuit. Once the optical section picks the pulse, it uses its amplifying circuit to increase the intensity, and this pulse is passed to the Arduino Nano microcontroller through the signal pin of the pulse rate sensor (How2electronics, 2022). The pulse rate sensor used in this work has an operating temperature range of -40 to +85 ° C, input voltage ranging from 3 to 5.5 V and supply current of between 3 and 4 A. The device used for location tracking and communication in this work is an A9G module. This module is based on RDA8955. It has the capacity for a voice call, (SMS), GPS, and serial to GPRS transmission. It can be used in many ways including an electricity facility and vehicle monitoring device, Internet of things applications to mention a few (DFrobot, 2022a). It supports Quad-band GSM/GPRS ranges of 850/900/1800/1900MHz. It has a working baud rate of 115200 bits per second during the sending of commands to GPS, GPRS, and so on and this can be modified by the user (DFrobot, 2022b). A9G module uses a SIM (subscriber identity module) module. In this work, a SIM from the MTN network in Nigeria is used.

The microcontroller used in this research is the Arduino Nano. This microcontroller is based on the Atmega 328 technology but is small and breadboard-friendly. Its operating voltage is 5 Volts. It has 8 analog pin 6 power pins and 14 digital pins as shown in figure 3. In this work, Arduino Nano is acting as the control unit coordinating different operations of the developed device (Arduino Nano, 2022). To activate a touch response in this work, a digital touch sensor is used. When this device is touched, a circuit closes and allows electric current to flow due to pressure applied and as such acting like a switch as shown in Figure 3. TTP22301 Digital Touch Sensor is used because it exhibits low power consumption - power supply for 2 - 5.5V dc but in this research 5 V was activated in the circuit the moment the touch sensor (switch) is closed as shown in Figure 3. The pulse sensor receives a 5 V from the microcontroller to be able to work as shown in Figure 3. It has a total of three pins (GND, VCC, and Sig). To power the Arduino Nano microcontroller, a Lithium Battery management system (BMS) providing 5 V is used.

Figure 1: Block Diagram of the system

Figure 2: Components connected together

Figure 3: Circuit diagram of the developed device

From Table 1, different components with their operating voltages are shown including the digital touch sensor with 5 V, A9G module with 4 V and the Arduino Nano with 5 V.

Table 1: Components with their different operating voltages

Component	Operating voltage (V)
Digital Touch sensor	5
A9G module	4
Arduino Nano	5
Pulse sensor	5

The A9G network module in the Arduino establishes communication between the transmitting end (the wearer) and the receiving end using a predetermined GSM number. The Nano microcontroller regulates and controls the system and the pulse sensor receives pulse input to determine if the user is still alive. The flowchart in Figure 4 describes the operation of the developed device. Wherever the user of the developed device senses danger and switches it on by pressing a push button, the system initializes to ensure all its communication ports are activated and ready for data transmission. The system immediately begins to read the user's pulse from the pulse sensor to determine the user's heart rate.

Figure 4: Flowchart of the System

When the user presses the digital touch sensor, GSM/GPRS modules are activated and transmit the user's location and pulse rate to mobile numbers which have been specified in the device. After this, it goes back to system initialization and this loop continues until the device is switched off.

3.2 Software Requirement

The software section involves the development of an algorithm for this system as shown in the flowchart using Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE). The algorithm was uploaded into the Arduino Nano microcontroller. The device uses AT commands to relay information between the A9G, GPS, GSM modules, and the Arduino Nano.

4. Results and Discussion

The system components were connected together forming a single package with a band-like fabric that allows it to be strapped to the user's arm above the elbow as shown in Figure 5a. This allows the pulse sensor to be in close contact with the user's body.

4.1 Distress Message Test

Tests were carried out by making the user wear the device and operate it by pressing the push button to evaluate system performance based on response time to distress messages, GPS

connection time, and response status. Response time is how long it takes for the distress text message to reach the mobile phone of relevant stakeholders whose numbers are pre-set in the device. This can be security agents or the user's family members. GPS connection time is how long it takes for Google Maps to update the geographical location of the victim after the link sent to the stakeholder's phone has been redirected. For response status, the device reports whether or not the message was sent.

Figure 5: a) Device strapped on the arm b) using bounce geolocator to find the victim's position

4.2 Bounce Geolocator Test

Apart from the victim sending distress call to relatives and security agents, the developed device also gives opportunity to the rescue agents to use its bounce geolocator capability to search for current location of the victim as the search operation progresses. This is achieved by a rescue agency member sending the code "location" as text message in the mobile App developed for the device which must have been installed on his mobile phone as shown in Figure 6a. This location is transmitted to the orbital satellite which responds by sending the Google Map address of the victim through a reply text message received by the rescue agent requesting the location. By clicking on the received Google Map address on the App in Figure 6a, a Google Map interface is displayed on the mobile phone showing the exact location of the victim and his pulse rate in realtime. This is illustrated in Figure 6b.

4.3 Discussion of Results

From Table 2, and Figure 7, it can be observed that ten (10) tests were carried out. The system response time to distress messages ranged between 5 and 7 seconds. The average response time is 5.7 seconds and this is good enough for stakeholders' response in case of an emergency. In the case of GPS connectivity, returned values ranged between 12 seconds and 76 seconds. In some cases, the GPS was not able to connect and as such returned no value. Only 4 out of 10 tests returned GPS values. This was largely based on where the device was being used. It was found that in most areas with a slight enclosure, it was hard to receive GPS signals and that the signals were stronger when the user was outside in the open space. This aligns with the findings of Emem et al., (2022). In terms of response status, the device returned positive results in ten trials. The indication of this was that in each of the 10 tests carried out, the device was able to

send out distress messages received by the stakeholders ten times. Figure 6a is the distress message received by relevant stakeholders on their mobile devices. From Figure 6a, it could be observed that the message received by stakeholders (victim's relations or security agents) on their mobile phones contained the pulse rate of the victim reading 81 BMP and 162 BMP in messages sent at different times as well as the current location of the user (victim). The current location is shown using a Google Map website address. This result implies that by monitoring the pulse rate of the user (victim) one can observe if the victim is still alive or not. For example, a 0 BMP could mean that the device is no longer on the user's body or he or she is no longer breathing. A pulse rate that is too high or too low could be used by medical experts to determine the health status of the user (victim). The bounce geolocator test also provides a means by which the rescue mission can continually track the current position of the victim by sending location code to the orbital satellite. This feature is a unique contribution of this work as compared to Emem et al., 2022 and Khan et al., 2021. All this information can help security operative to plan their rescue mission for example going with medical personnel or arranging for an ambulance in cases where it is suspected that the health of the victim requires emergency intervention. This pulse rate information depicting the health status of the victim distinguishes this work from (Emem, et al., 20220; Khan et al, 2019; Khan et al, 2021) which only provides information about the current location of the victim and nothing about the rules rate or health status.

Figure 6: a) Distress messages displaying the user's current location by Google map address and users pulse rate (BMP) b) Google Map interface showing the current location of the victim

Table 2: System performance analysis table

S/N	Response Time (s)	GPS connection time (s)	Response status
1	5	12	Yes
2	7	12	Yes
3	5	-	Yes
4	7	-	Yes
5	6	-	Yes
6	5	-	Yes
7	6	-	Yes
8	5	-	Yes
9	5	76	Yes
10	6	81	Yes

Figure 7: Graph of system performance test

5. Conclusion

The project developed a pulse rate-enabled human tracking system with an integrated bounce geolocator. This device does not only reveal the current location of the victim on Google Maps but gives information to determine if the victim is alive as well as the possible health status of the victim through its pulse rate sensor. The portability and ease of use of the developed device would make it a valuable tool in mitigating the challenge of insurgency, kidnapping, and banditry being experienced in Nigeria and many African countries. How to improve the sensitivity of the GPS receiver will be the focus of future work.

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